

LEGAL REGULATION OF NOTARY'S LIABILITY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: A notary in the Republic of Uzbekistan is a legal institution designed to ensure the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of individuals and legal entities through the performance by notaries of notarial actions provided for by law and directly related actions of a legal and technical nature.

Active participation of a notary in the Republic of Uzbekistan in market legal relations predetermines the need to ensure a high level of legal regulation of his activities.

Key words: Republic of Uzbekistan, Ministry of Justice, Notarial acts, State Tax Committee.

Notarial acts in the Republic of Uzbekistan are performed in accordance with the Law "On Notaries" and other legislative acts by notaries of state notary offices and notaries engaged in private practice. The register of notaries is maintained by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1].

Notarial acts on the territory of other states are performed by consuls of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

A notary, other officials performing notarial acts, as well as persons who have become aware of the notarial acts performed in connection with the performance of their official duties, are prohibited from disclosing information that has become known to them, including after the termination of the employment contract.

Information (documents) on notarial acts performed may be issued only to persons on whose behalf or on whose behalf these actions were performed. Certificates (information) on notarial acts performed are issued at the request of the

court, the prosecutor's office, the bodies of inquiry and investigation in connection with the cases in their proceedings.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, notarial acts are carried out in the state language. At the request of citizens, the text of the executed document by a notary or a person performing notarial acts is issued in Russian or, if possible, in another acceptable language.

The current legislation in the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for certain legal mechanisms to ensure the compliance of notarial acts performed by notaries with the law.

Such security legal mechanisms may include the consolidation in the law of legal guarantees of notarial activity, in particular, the impartiality and independence of notaries, the licensing of notarial activities and the qualification selection of candidates for the position of notaries, the organizational and legal support of notaries' activities by the notary chambers of the constituent entities of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In 2011, the Netherlands announced that it. According to the law, a notary is obliged to assist individuals and legal entities in exercising their rights and protecting their legitimate interests, to explain to them their rights and obligations, including, to explain to the parties the meaning and significance of the draft transactions submitted by them and to check whether their content corresponds to the real intentions of the parties and whether they do not contradict the requirements of the law. to warn individuals and legal entities about the consequences of notarial acts so that legal ignorance cannot be used to their detriment, to refuse to perform a notarial act in case of its non-compliance with the law, in case of detection of a violation of the law by citizens or officials during the performance of notarial acts, to inform the relevant enterprises about it so that the relevant enterprises can take the necessary measures, institutions, organizations or prosecutors, at least once every three years, to improve their professional qualifications, to issue, at the request of the court, the prosecutor's office, the bodies of inquiry and investigation, certificates (information) on the notarial

actions performed in connection with the cases in the proceedings of these bodies; submit to the specially authorized state body certificates (information) on the performed notarial actions related to combating the legalization of proceeds from crime, the financing of terrorism and the financing of the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction, submit to the body of the state tax service certificates on the certification of contracts for the sale and purchase of real estate, property lease agreements and the amount of rent, and also on the value of property transferred by way of inheritance or gift to the ownership of citizens, to submit to the internal affairs body certificates on the certification of powers of attorney for the right to use and (or) dispose of, contracts of alienation, lease, gratuitous use, pledge, leasing of motor vehicles.

Submit to the Karakalpak Republican, regional, Tashkent city departments of the Chamber of State Cadastres of the Cadastre Agency under the State Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in accordance with the legislation, information on the cadastral number of the alienated real estate and on the acquirer [2].

At the request of credit bureaus, provide certificates (information) on the absence of prohibition of alienation or arrest of the object that is the subject of the transaction, submit, at the request of the real estate organization, certificates (information) on the absence of prohibition of alienation or arrest of the real estate object that is the subject of the transaction, submit certificates of testament to interested persons after the death of the testator, provide, at the request of the Chamber of Accounts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, information on the notarial actions performed.

To pay to the Chamber of Notaries the entrance and membership fees, the amount of which is established by the Conference of the Chamber of Notaries.

A necessary and important feature of the institution of a free notary of the Latin type is the full property liability of a private notary for illegal acts committed by him.

A notary engaged in private practice is obliged to conclude a contract of insurance of civil liability of a notary when he carries out his notarial activities.

A notary engaged in private practice is not entitled to perform his/her duties and perform notarial acts without concluding a civil liability insurance contract.

The object of insurance under the civil liability insurance contract is property interests associated with the risk of liability of a notary engaged in private practice for obligations arising as a result of causing property damage to an individual or legal entity who has applied for a notarial act, and (or) to third parties in the course of notarial activities.

An insured event under a notary's civil liability insurance contract is a court decision established by a court decision that has entered into legal force or is recognized by the insurer as a result of a notarial act that contradicts the law.

The sum insured under the civil liability insurance contract of a notary engaged in private practice may not be less than:

for the organization of the activities of a notary engaged in private practice in the cities of Tashkent, Nukus and administrative centers of the regions - at least a thousand times the size of the basic calculated value;

for the organization of the activities of a notary engaged in private practice in other localities - at least five hundred times the size of the basic calculated value [3].

In France, the civil liability of notaries, which allows the client to compensate for the damage caused by the notary's error, is organized on two levels, the first of which is compulsory insurance. Until recently, each notary was obliged to do this individually. Since the Law of February 2004, notaries have been obliged to conclude a civil liability insurance contract within the framework of a national contract, which is signed for all notaries by the Higher Council of Notaries. A French notary thus does not choose his insurer or the amount of insurance or premium. All this is done within the framework of a nationwide insurance contract.

This insurance contract covers the entire amount of damage that may be caused by the notary. The insurance ceiling for one case is 30 million euros. Additional insurance can be carried out at the level of regional councils – there are 33 of them in total – based on the assumption that the notaries of these regional councils can certify notarial acts for larger amounts [4].

References:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 14, 2020 No. ZRU-602- National Database of Legislation, 15.01.2020, No03/20/602/00521
2. Раджабов О.А. __История развития железнодорожного транспорта в Узбекистане // Актуальные вопросы, открытия и достижения: сборник статей XXVIII Международной научно-практической конференции. – Пенза: МЦНС «Наука и Просвещение», 2021. – С. 94-97.
3. Law of the Republic Uzbekistan from January 14, 2020 No. ZRU-602- National Database of Legislation, 15.01.2020, No. 03/20/602/0052.
4. Radjabov O. _Railways of Uzbekistan During the Second World War // European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (EJLSS) ISSN 2660-9630. – Volume 11, 2021. – Pp.195-197. (№23. SJIF Impact Factor 2021:5,63).